

README for Producing Health: Measuring the Value Added of Nursing Homes

March 7, 2025

1 Data availability statement and raw data

There are many datasets used in this paper. Almost all of them are proprietary and CMS must approve a DUA with researchers for access to these data. Therefore, this paper is exempt from submitting actual raw data for replication. We provide fake versions of all datasets in our replication kit so other researchers can easily run our code. Fake data are provided in .csv format. The data are described below.

- The Minimum Data Set (MDS) 3.0: These data are provided by CMS. It may take many months to write a DUA and obtain the data from CMS. We used these data from 2011 through 2016 and we originally accessed the data in 2019.
- The Master Beneficiary Summary File: These are data on Medicare beneficiaries provided by CMS including basic demographics, Part A/B/C participation, and chronic conditions. It may take many months to write a DUA to obtain the data from CMS. We used these data from 2011 through 2016 and we originally accessed the data in 2019.
- Medicare Provider Analysis and Review (MedPAR): These data provide information on Medicare claims for SNFs and inpatient stays. It may take many months to write a DUA and obtain the data from CMS. We used these data from 2011 through 2016 and we originally accessed the data in 2019.
- LTCFocus OSCAR and CASPER Data: These data provide information on SNFs collected by CMS with the OSCAR and CASPER surveys. We used data from 2011 through 2016 and accessed it for the first time in 2019. To ease replication we have provided a fake version of these data in the replication kit. These data can be downloaded [here](#).
- Geographic crosswalks: We use a variety of geographic crosswalks that are publicly available. To facilitate replication, we have create fake versions of these in the replication kit. These data were all accessed for the first time in 2019.
 - SSA to Federal Information Processing Series (FIPS) Core-Based Statistical Area (CBSA) and Metropolitan and Micropolitan Statistical Area (MSA) County Crosswalk: can be downloaded [here](#)
 - ArcGIS Geocoded HSA centroids from HSA shape files: can be downloaded [here](#)
 - ZIP code to HSA to HRR crosswalk files from Dartmouth Atlas for 2012: can be downloaded [here](#)

- Geocoded zip centroids: can be downloaded [here](#)

2 Metadata summary

All CMS datasets have detailed documentation on ResDAC. Links to websites that include appropriate documentation can be found in the data citation section below.

3 Replication package

The replication package has 6 folders. To run all code in the replication kit follow the following instructions in order

1. Unzip the replication folder (e.g., `tar -xf replication_kit.tar.gz`)
2. Download Julia binaries for version 1.7.2 [here](#) or if you have a linux operating system unzip the binaries that are already included in the replication_kit folder. Place the julia binaries in the replication_kit folder (this will create a 7th folder in the replication_kit directory called julia-1.7.2). Please install all other software as described in Section 5.
3. Set the global path to the replication_kit folder in make.py in the code folder. Then run the make.py file using python.
4. Do not move any of the folders inside the replication kit folder. Our replication kit is internally consistent and runs on relative file paths so run it as is. If you intend to move any folders you must change the filepaths in all of the code files.
5. All output is in output/figures and output/tables. Only check the output after the make.py script finishes running. Section 4 describes where each exhibit can be found. Output can be compared to the output saved in replication_output to make sure the exhibits are reproducible.

The following folders are included in the replication kit

- code: Contains all code needed to create results. The file make.py runs all of the code at once.
- externals: Contains fake datasets and processed data
- external_links: Contains fake datasets and processed data
- output: Contains output of the code. Subfolders figures and tables contain all exhibits in the paper and the appendices.
- temp: Contains temporary files.
- replication_output: Our output from running the replication so other researchers can compare their output to this output
- R: an empty directory to store R libraries when installed in the code

If you intend to run the code without the make.py master script the code must be run in the following order. Also, please note that the replication kit uses relative file paths so you must cd into each directory to run each code file. The master script does this automatically so it is best practice to run the code with the master script.

1. MergeMSA/build.do
2. Subsample/build.do
3. CleanData/build.do
4. CreateHealthMeasures/build.do
5. StayLevelSample/build.do
6. ICDtoCCS/build.do
7. CleanMedPAR/build.do
8. LinkMedPAR/build.do
9. LinkMedicare/build.do
10. non-mdcrStayLevel/build.do
11. LinkOSCAR/build.do
12. RestrictedSamp/build.do
13. PredDschrgToComm/prep_data.do
14. PredDschrgToComm/build_v2.R
15. PredDschrgToComm/build_post.do
16. PredDschrgToCommRobust/prep_data.do
17. PredDschrgToCommRobust/build_v2.R
18. PredDschrgToCommRobust/build_post.do
19. PrepDschrgModel/build.do
20. PrepDschrgModelRobust/build.do
21. HotDeck/build.do
22. HotDeckRobust/build.do
23. SplitHRRs/build.do
24. DistToSNFs/build.do
25. DemandWithCovariates/prep_parallel.do
26. DemandWithCovariates/parallel.bash

27. DemandWithCovariates/post_demand.do
28. DemandWithCovariates/parallel_bs.bash
29. DemandWithCovariates/post_demand_bs.do
30. DemandNoCovariates/prep_parallel.do
31. DemandNoCovariates/parallel.bash
32. DemandADL/prep_parallel.do
33. DemandADL/parallel_analysis.bash
34. DemandByAge/prep_parallel.do
35. DemandByAge/parallel_analysis.bash
36. DemandByMedicaid/prep_parallel.do
37. DemandByMedicaid/parallel_analysis.bash
38. HeckmanUpstreamDownstreamSubHRRs/analysis.do
39. HeckmanUpstreamDownstreamSubHRRs/prob_ach.jl
40. HeckmanUpstreamDownstreamSubHRRs/assemble_spec.m
41. HeckmanUpstreamDownstreamSubHRRs/phi_combs.do
42. HeckmanUpstreamDownstream3/analysis.do
43. HeckmanUpstreamDownstream3/prob_ach.jl
44. HeckmanUpstreamDownstream3/assemble_spec.m
45. HeckmanUpstreamDownstreamNoCovars/analysis.do
46. HeckmanUpstreamDownstreamNoCovars/prob_ach.jl
47. HeckmanUpstreamDownstreamNoCovars/assemble_spec.m
48. HeckmanUpstreamDownstreamNoCovars/prob_ach_ses.jl
49. HeckmanUpstreamDownstreamNoCovars/ses.do
50. HeckmanUpstreamDownstreamNoCovars/phi_combs.do
51. ScoreBootstrapStep1/prep_parallel.do
52. ScoreBootstrapStep1/parallel.bash
53. ScoreBootstrapStep2/analysis.do
54. ScoreBootstrapStep2/prob_ach.jl
55. ScoreBootstrapStep2/ses.do

56. BayesShrink/analysis.do
57. HeckmanUpstreamDownstreamByAge/analysis.do 1
58. HeckmanUpstreamDownstreamByAge/analysis.do 2
59. HeckmanUpstreamDownstreamByAge/analysis.do 3
60. HeckmanUpstreamDownstreamByAge/prob_ach.jl
61. HeckmanUpstreamDownstreamByAge/assemble_spec.m
62. HeckmanUpstreamDownstreamByAge/ses.do
63. HeckmanUpstreamDownstreamByAge/ebshrink.do
64. HeckmanUpstreamDownstreamByMedicaid/analysis.do 0
65. HeckmanUpstreamDownstreamByMedicaid/analysis.do1
66. HeckmanUpstreamDownstreamByMedicaid/prob_ach.jl
67. HeckmanUpstreamDownstreamByMedicaid/assemble_spec.m
68. HeckmanUpstreamDownstreamByMedicaid/ses.do
69. HeckmanUpstreamDownstreamByMedicaid/ebshrink.do
70. HeckmanUpstreamDownstreamRobustH/analysis.do
71. HeckmanUpstreamDownstreamRobustH/prob_ach.jl
72. HeckmanUpstreamDownstreamRobustH/assemble_spec.m
73. HeckmanUpstreamDownstreamRobustH/ses.do
74. HeckmanUpstreamDownstreamRobustH/ebshrink.do
75. ADLVAM/analysis.do
76. ADLVAM/prob_ach.jl
77. ADLVAM/assemble_spec.m
78. ADLVAM/ses.do
79. ADLVAM/ebshrink.do
80. SelectionOutVAM/analysis.do
81. SelectionOutVAM/prob_ach.jl
82. SelectionOutVAM/assemble_spec.m
83. SelectionOutVAM/ses.do
84. SelectionOutVAM/ebshrink.do

85. Healthindex/analysis.do
86. LengthOfStay/analysis.do
87. InvestigateInstruments/analysis.do
88. MakeRestrictsTable/build.do
89. SampleSummary/analysis.do
90. ModelFit/analysis.do
91. CompareVAMsByGroup/analysis.do
92. CounterfactualsSubHRRsRobust/analysis.do
93. DschrgModelPooled/analysis.do
94. DschrgTiming/analysis.do
95. ValidateVAMs90DaysSubHRRs/analysis.do
96. CounterfactualsSubHRRs/analysis.do
97. CounterfactualsADL/analysis.do
98. CompareHealthIndicesAltDschrg/analysis.do
99. AnalysisHotDeck/analysis.do

4 Exhibit locations

This section describes where all exhibits can be found.

4.1 Main figures

- Figure 1 (Movement and measurement of patients) is a diagram containing no data. This was made by hand by the researchers.
- Figure 2 (Health index)
 - Panel A (Distribution of health index at admission)
 - * hist_h1.pdf can be found in output/figures
 - Panel B (Health index at admission and length of stay)
 - * scatter_los_h_w1_dschrg_comm.pdf can be found in output/figures
- Figure 3 (Distance instrument for selection in)
 - Panel A (Chicago HRR)
 - * marginsplots.pdf can be found in output/figures
 - Panel B (All markets)

- * scatter_first stage.pdf can be found in output/figures
- Figure 4 (Value added)
 - Panel A (National parameters)
 - * natl_params.txt in output/tables
 - Panel B (Value added vs. discharge threshold)
 - * value_added_vs_lambda_j_new.pdf can be found in output/figures/cfactsbhrr
 - Panel C (Value added vs. selection coefficient)
 - * value_added_vs_phi_k_new.pdf can be found in output/figures/cfactsbhrr
- Figure 5 (Empirical Bayes shrinkage)
 - Panel A (Kernel densities with and without empirical Bayes (EB) shrinkage)
 - * spec_3_bs_bayes_overlay_density.pdf can be found in output/figures
 - Panel B (Distribution of EB-adjusted value added)
 - * value_added_hist_new.pdf can be found in output/figures/cfactsbhrr
- Figure 6 (Heterogeneity across and within markets):
 - Panel A (Average value added by market): map_value_added_new.pdf can be found in output/figures/cfactsbhrr
 - Panel B (90-10 difference in value added by market): map_gains_new.pdf can be found in output/figures/cfactsbhrr
 - Panel C (Distr. of value added): across_within_stats_new.txt can be found in output/tables/cfactsbhrr
- Figure 7 (Dispersion in value added within markets)
 - boxplots_value_added_10_90_new.pdf can be found in output/figures/cfactsbhrr
- Figure 8 (Correlating CMS star ratings and value added at the market level)
 - value_added_vs_stars_new.pdf can be found in output/figures/cfactsbhrr

4.2 Main tables

- Table 1 (*Patient characteristics*)
 - sum_stats_trim.txt can be found in output/tables
- Table 2 (*SNF characteristics*)
 - SNFChars.txt can be found in output/tables
- Table 3 (*Selected health index measures*)
 - phats_by_x.txt can be found in output/tables
- Table 4 (*Health index*)

- fit_more_raw.txt can be found in output/tables
- Table 5 (Upstream discharge parameters)
 - gamma_stats_new.pdf can be found in output/tables/cfactsbhrr
- Table 6 (Correlations of value-added estimates with SNF and patient characteristics)
 - SNFcorrelates_new_more.txt can be found in output/tables/cfactsbhrr
- Table 7 (Distribution of value added for alternative measures and specifications)
 - Panel A (Baseline)
 - * across_within_stats_new.txt can be found in output/tables/cfactsbhrr
 - Panel B (ADLs)
 - * across_within_stats_adl.txt can be found in output/tables
 - Panel C (Excluding incentivized measures)
 - * across_within_stats_robust.txt can be found in output/tables
 - Panel D (By patient characteristics)
 - * across_within_stats_dual.txt can be found in output/tables
- Table 8 (Correlations of value-added estimates with alternative measures)
 - corr_specs_table.txt can be found in output/tables

4.3 Appendix figures

- Appendix Figure A1 (Discharge within 7 days of 30-day assessment vs. h_{i2})
 - dschrg_rate_vs_h_w4_X.pdf can be found in output/figures for X = (A) all, (B) high, (C) med, (D) low, (E) overlaid
- Appendix Figure A2 (Weekly discharge rule)
 - dschrg_plot_comm.pdf can be found in output/figures
- Appendix Figure A3 (Correlating coefficient on log-distance)
 - first_stage_robust.pdf can be found in output/figures
- Appendix Figure A4 (Correlating difference between 90th and 10th percentile VA within market with average VA in market)
 - scatter_gains_los_nat_new.pdf can be found in output/figures/cfactsbhrr
- Appendix Figure A5 (Correlates of SNF value added)
 - value_added_vs_X_new.pdf can be found in output/figures/cfactsbhrr for X = (A) oscar_occpect, (B) oscar_totbeds, (C) oscar_profit, (D) oscar_hospbase, (E) oscar_multifac, (F) oscar_paymcare, (G) oscar_alzunit, (H) h_w1, (I) mds_black, (J) medicaid, (K) mds_female, (L) mds_married, (M) mds_age

- Appendix Figure A6 (Correlations of value added estimates with alternative measures)
 - binscatter_X_vs_value_added_market_fe.pdf can be found in output/figures for X = (A) adl, (B) incent, (C) overall_rating, (D) quality_rating, (E) inspection_rating, (F) staffing_rating, (G) FE_los, (H) FE_home, (I) FE_spending, (J) FE_readmit_medpar, (K) FE_readmit_hosp, (L) FE_died, (M) spec1, (N) spec3, (O) spec4, (P) spec5
- Appendix Figure A7 (Correlating value added estimates by age group)
 - binsc_alpha_age_X_age_Y_all.pdf can be found in output/figures for (X,Y) = (A) (1, 2), (B) (1, 3), (C) (2, 3)
- Appendix Figure A8 (Correlating value added estimates by Medicaid status)
 - binsc_alpha_dual_0_dual_1_all.pdf can be found in output/figures
- Appendix Figure A9 (Correlating estimates by age group against estimates by Medicaid status)
 - binsc_alpha_age_X_dual_Y_all.pdf can be found in output/figures for (X,Y) = (A) (1,0), (B) (2, 0), (C) (3,0), (D) (1,1), (E) (2, 1), (F) (3, 1)
- Appendix Figure A10 (Heath index with alternative discharge definition)
 - binsc_h_wX_overall.pdf for X = (A) 1, (C) 4, binsc_h_wX_hrr.pdf for X = (B) 1, (D) 4 can be found in output/figures
- Appendix Figure A11 (Differences in discharge timing)
 - hist_diff_mean.pdf, binsc_alpha_diff_mean.pdf can be found in output/figures

4.4 Appendix tables

- Appendix Table A1 (Sample restrictions)
 - restricts.txt can be found in output/tables
- Appendix Table A2 (List of health measures used)
 - measures_table_combined_v1_table.txt can be found in output/tables
- Appendix Table A3 (Alternative discharge models)
 - coefs.txt can be found in output/tables
- Appendix Table A4 (Health index fit for all patients in a SNF at 30 days)
 - appendix_fit.txt can be found in output/tables
- Appendix Table A5 (Discharge destinations by 30-day assessment availability)
 - dschrg_w4_stats.txt can be found in output/tables
- Appendix Table A6 (Imputation Procedure) is a flowchart containing no data.

- Appendix Table A7 (Summary statistics by imputation cases)
 - in_week_4.txt can be found in output/tables
- Appendix Table A8 (Alternative health index with new discharge definition)
 - h_stats.txt can be found in output/tables
- Appendix Table A9 (National parameters estimated for alternative measures and specifications)
 - baseline: natl_params.txt, adls: natl_params_adl.txt, excluding incentivized: natl_params_robust.txt, by age: natl_params_age1.txt, natl_params_age2.txt, natl_params_age3.txt,
 - by medicaid: natl_params_dual0.txt, natl_params_dual1.txt

5 Software and hardware

Software used includes

- STATA MP version 18
 - Stata libraries are included in the externals folder in ado and gslab_misc/ado
 - Required libraries include
 - * gtools v1.10.1
 - * ftools v2.49.1
 - * egenmore v3.4.2
 - * maptile v1.0.5
 - * spmap v1.0.5
 - * reghdfe v5.7.3
 - * geodist v1.1.0
- Matlab version R2021a or later
 - no required libraries
- Julia version 1.7.2
 - all required libraries are installed in the code and the linux julia binary used is included in the replication kit. to install 1.7.2 binaries for different operating systems, see [here](#)
 - Required libraries include
 - * CSV version 0.10.15
 - * DataFrames version 1.7.0
 - * VectorizedRoutines version 0.1.0
 - * Distributions version 0.1.0
 - * ForwardDiff 0.10.38
 - * LinearAlgebra version 0.1.0
 - * Optim version 1.11.0

- R version 4.4.1 or later
 - all required libraries are installed in the code
 - Required libraries include
 - * rpart version 4.1.24
 - * e1071 version 1.7-16
 - * rpart.plot version 3.1.2
 - * caret version 7.0-1
 - * Hmisc version 5.2-2
 - * foreign version 0.8-88
 - * data.table version 1.17.0
 - * ROCR version 1.0-11
 - * dplyr version 1.1.4
- Python version 2.7.18 or later
 - required libraries include
 - * os
 - * subprocess

Hardware used includes

- a server with 64 CPU cores and 2101 GB of memory

Stata is needed for every code directory. Matlab and Julia are only needed for the HeckmanUpstream-Downstream, ADLVAM, and SelectionOutVAM directories. R is only needed for the PredDschrgToComm directories. Python is only needed to run the make.py which executes all of the code at once.

On fake data the code runs in an hour and twenty minutes. On real data the code will take about a month to run. The vast majority of the runtime is spent in the Demand code directories and the HeckmanUpstreamDownstream code directories. Without these directories the code should run in less than a week.

6 Data citations

References

- [1] Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services. 2024a. *Long Term Care Minimum Data Set (MDS) 3.0*. <https://resdac.org/cms-data/files/mds-30>.
- [2] Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services. 2024b. *Master Beneficiary Summary File*. <https://resdac.org/cms-data/files/mbsf-base>.
- [3] Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services. 2024c. *Medicare Provider Analysis and Review*. <https://resdac.org/cms-data/files/medpar>.
- [4] Long-Term Care: Facts on Care in the US. 2024. "About Us". <http://ltcfocus.org/about>.

- [5] National Bureau of Economic Research. 2024. *SSA to Federal Information Processing Series (FIPS) Core-Based Statistical Area (CBSA) and Metropolitan and Micropolitan Statistical Area (MSA) County Crosswalk*. <https://www.nber.org/research/data/ssa-federal-information-processing-series-fips-core-based-statistical-area-cbsa-and-metropolitan-and>
- [6] The Dartmouth Atlas. 2024. *Geographic Boundary Files*. <https://data.dartmouthatlas.org/supplemental/#boundaries>.
- [7] U.S. Department of Housing and Urban Development. 2024. *ZIP Code Population Weighted Centroids*. <https://catalog.data.gov/dataset/zip-code-population-weighted-centroids>.